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Ecotoxicological procedures for WP4

Hofman et al.

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Overall Project coordinator	Prof. Dr. V. GEISSEN (violette.geissen@wur.nl)
Scientific coordinator	Prof. Dr. P. SCHEEPERS (paul.scheepers@radboudumc.nl)
EU project officer	Bela ATZEL
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Author(s) of report (institution)	Jakub Hofman (MU), Nelson Abrantes (UA), Paula Tourinho (MU), Esperanza Huerta Lwanga (WU), Frank van Langevelde (WUR), Erin Henry (WUR), Paula Harkes (WU), Philipp Mäder (UH), Ellen Kandeler (UH)
Principle Author e-mail	jakub.hofman@recetox.muni.cz
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E--Mail(s)	
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Content

1	Introduction and general strategy.....	4
2	Terrestrial tests – EFSA standards	6
2.1	Soil microbial activity	6
2.2	Collembola.....	7
2.3	Earthworms	7
2.4	Beneficial insects	8
2.5	Bees	9
2.6	Plants	11
3	Terrestrial tests – new SPRINT indicators	12
3.1	Soil microcosms.....	12
3.2	Soil microbiome.....	13
3.3	Native earthworms.....	14
3.4	Native insects.....	14
4	Aquatic tests – EFSA standards	15
4.1	Microalgae	15
4.2	Aquatic plants	15
4.3	Aquatic insects	16
4.4	Fish	17
5	Aquatic tests – new SPRINT indicators	17
5.1	Multi-species microcosm assays	17
6	Conclusion	18
7	References.....	18

1 Introduction and general strategy

SPRINT aims to provide a set of tools and novel data needed for assessment of integrated risks and impacts of plant protection products (PPP; pesticides) on environment and human health. Using this, SPRINT wants to accelerate the adoption of innovative transition pathways towards more sustainable plant protection.

Ecotoxicological work within SPRINT will rely on the recently published EFSA guidance for risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals (EFSA, 2019). The ecotoxicological effects will be tested **not only on current EFSA organisms and tests**, but also on **alternative (native) species and in multi-species systems**, highlighting indirect and chronic effects, bioaccumulation and biomagnification, as well as better ecological relevance. This way, SPRINT will develop and validate a novel and/or improved strategy for testing the **integrated effects of PPP mixtures**. Improved ecotoxicological assays will be used for the testing of PPP mixtures identified in the case study sites (CSS).

The risk from exposure to chemical mixtures can be assessed as (Bopp et al. 2018; EFSA, 2019):

- testing the real or prepared mixtures (**whole-mixture approach**)
- mathematical predictions based on the individual components (**components-based approach**)

In the SPRINT project, we will practically follow a whole-mixture approach and we will **compare the results measured with the component-based predictions** (for the known components of the mixture).

After the identification of the main compounds (active substances – AS and/or transformation products – TP) in the real soil and water samples from each CSS, a maximum of **11 test mixtures** will be prepared consisting of **maximally 5 AS and/or TP per mixture**. With high probability, these will be different for soil and aquatic environment. Along with the frequency of detection and the concentrations measured, the selection of the top five compounds will be based on their eco-toxicological hazard, application rates, PPP properties (e.g. persistence, adsorption coefficient, solubility), mode of action, annual consumption and other factors.

Each mixture will be tested at **5 concentrations**:

- field concentration
- 3 additional concentrations
- control

Most of the tests will be performed with 4 replicates per concentration.

A **tiered approach**, from simple assessments at low-tier to more complex assessments at high-tier, will be implemented based on the EFSA guidelines for combined exposure to multiple chemicals (EFSA, 2019). Ecotoxicological effects on the terrestrial and aquatic environment will be evaluated using both:

- **low-tier standard single-species EFSA tests**
- **“new SPRINT indicators”** using
 - several alternative (native) species
 - higher-tier multi-species microcosms

The overview of the ecotoxicological procedures for SPRINT is shown in the following table and the chapters elucidate more details on the individual procedures.

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Test organisms	Indicators (references)	Duration (days)	Source for single AS/TP data
Terrestrial: EFSA tests			
Soil microbial activity	Carbon and nitrogen mineralization - Cmin, Nmin (OECD 2000a,b; ISO 2012e; ISO 2012f; ISO 1997; ISO 2005)	28 -100	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases
Collembola (<i>Folsomia candida</i> , <i>F. firmentaria</i>)	Mortality, reproductivity (ISO 2014; OECD 2016b)	21-28	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases.
Earthworms (<i>Eisenia fetida</i> , <i>E. andrei</i>)	Mortality, reproduction, growth (OECD 1984; OECD 2016a; ISO 2012a; ISO 2012b)	14, 56	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases.
Beneficial insects (e.g. <i>Aphidius rhopalosiphi</i> , <i>Typhlodromus pyri</i>)	Mortality, reproductivity (Mead-Briggs et al. 2000, Blümel et al. 2000).	2, 7, 14	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases.
Honey bees (<i>Apis mellifera</i>)	Colony size, amount of food, amount of brood, mortality, gut microbiome	7, 28, 90	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases.
Terrestrial plants (e.g. <i>Lactuca sativa</i>)	Root growth (ISO 11269-1); emergence & early growth (ISO 11269-2, OECD 208).	days to months	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases.
Terrestrial: New SPRINT indicators			
Soil microcosms (native earthworm, <i>L. sativa</i> , microbial communities)	Survival and reproduction of earthworms, plant growth, plants shoot/root, bioaccumulation in earthworms and plants, microbial activities (Cmin, Nmin) (Šudoma et al. 2019; Fojtová et al. 2019; Šudoma et al. 2021; Kandeler et al. 2019)	84	Literature (limited)
Soil microbiome - Functional and structural biodiversity	Soil microbiome; PLFAs, microbial carbon and nitrogen, enzymes involved in C-, N- and P-cycling (Kandeler et al. 2019)	28, 56, 84	Literature
Native earthworm species (anecic, endogeic, epigeic) from CSS	Mortality, reproductivity	90, 150, 365	Literature, (eco)toxicological databases
Native beneficial insects from CSS	Mortality, changes in community structure	7, 28, 90	Literature
Wild bees (<i>Bombus terrestris</i>)	Nesting activity of solitary bee species, colony development of the bumblebee	7, 28, 90	Literature
Aquatic: EFSA tests			
Freshwater algae (<i>Raphidocelis subcapitata</i>)	Growth inhibition (OECD 2011a)	3	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases
Freshwater plant (<i>Lemna</i> sp.)	Growth inhibition (OECD 2006a)	7	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases
Freshwater insects (<i>Chironomus</i> sp.)	Larval survival and growth, number of adults emerged (OECD 2004)	20-28	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases.
Fish (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	Fish embryo toxicity test (FET) (OECD 2013)	48h	EFSA reports, literature, (eco)toxicological databases
Aquatic: New SPRINT indicators			
Aquatic microcosm (producers, first and second consumers)	Bioaccumulation, trophic transfer	14	Literature

2 Terrestrial tests – EFSA standards

2.1 Soil microbial activity

Microbial activities play an essential role in the decomposition and cycling of nutrients, and therefore are a good bioindicator of the health status of soils. Nevertheless, the potential effects of PPP mixtures on microbial activities have been poorly addressed so far. In the SPRINT project, carbon and nitrogen transformations will be used to assess these effects. The soil used for the testing of PPP mixture effects on soil microbial activities should be sampled and stored according to ISO 10381-6 (ISO 2009). This means the effect of the sampling and storage on the vitality of the soil microorganisms is kept on minimum. The soil will be stored at 4°C before the testing and sieved through 2 mm mesh. Before the tests, the soil will be re-vitalized by pre-incubation at the 40-60% water-holding capacity (WHC) at 22°C. As the testing soil, LUFA 2.1 will be probably used.

Soil will be spiked with PPP mixtures at 4 concentrations plus a control. When necessary, a solvent control will be included. The soil will be incubated in bulk at 22 °C in the dark. After 0, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days of incubation, four replicates will be prepared per treatment, by transferring soil samples to infusion bottles or centrifuge tubes. The samples will be prepared in accordance with each measurement (see below), and after 24 h, carbon and nitrogen transformation will be assessed. If, after 28 days of incubation, the difference between treated and control soils are $\geq 25\%$, the tests will be continued for up to 100 days. Test design can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Test design for determining soil microbial activity.

Carbon transformation will be measured using basal respiration (BR) and substrate-induced respiration (SIR) methods adapted from ISO guidelines 16072 and 14240-1, respectively (ISO 2005; ISO 1997). For BR, the production of CO₂ will be measured by gas chromatography (GC, Agilent Technologies 6850), by sampling the air from the jars with a syringe. For SIR, glucose will be added to the soils as substrate to induce respiration and water content will be adjust to 80% WHC. After 2, 4, and 6 h, the CO₂ production will be measured by GC, also by sampling air from the jars with a syringe.

For nitrogen transformation, the potential of ammonification (PAMO) and potential nitrification (PAO) will be measured. PAMO will be done according to Alef (1995). At each time point, 2 g of soil will be placed in polystyrene tubes. L-arginine solution will be added to samples, vortex mixed and incubated at 30 °C for 3 h. Control measurements will be done by adding distilled water and samples will be stored in the freezer for 3 h. Then, 1M KCl solution will be added to the tubes, vortex mixed and shaken at 150 rpm for 45 min. Tubes will be centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 5 min and supernatant filtered and analyzed for ammonium ions by flow injection (FIALab 2500). PAO will be measured according to ISO 15685 (ISO 2012f). Solution containing ammonium sulphate is added to the soil and after incubation with sodium chlorate (inhibits oxidation of nitrites to nitrates), the nitrite ions are determined by flow injection analysis. Optionally, long term incubation with periodical N-mineral forms measurements can be performed according to ISO (2012e).

2.2 Collembola

Collembola are soil-dwelling organisms with great ecological relevance for the soil ecosystem. *Folsomia candida* is a parthenogenetic species and has a high rate of reproduction. Moreover, this species is easy to culture under laboratory conditions. Therefore, *F. candida* has been widely used as a model organism in soil ecotoxicology studies.

A reproduction test with the specie *Folsomia candida* will be performed following the ISO and OECD protocols (ISO 2014; OECD 2016b). Lufa soil will be spiked at 4 concentrations of PPP mixtures and a control. Four replicates per treatment will be prepared. One day before starting the tests, soil will be spiked with the PPP mixtures. If PPP mixture is added in solvent, a solvent control will be prepared, and the samples will be allowed to evaporate overnight under a fume hood. Soil pH will be measured at the beginning of the test. Springtails (10-12 days old) will be obtained by synchronizing the egg laying of the culture animals. The tests will be conducted in glass jars containing approximately 30 g moist artificial soil (50% WHC) (Figure 2). At the start of the test, 10 animals will be transferred into each test jar and 2 mg dried yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) will be added as food source. Test jars will be incubated in a climate room at 20 ± 1 °C and a photoperiod of 16 h:8 h (light:dark). Moisture loss will be replenished weekly, and food will be added biweekly. After 28 days, the test is ended by adding tap water to the test jars. The content will be transferred into a beaker glass, stirred carefully to let all the animals float on the surface and photographed with a digital camera. The number of adults and juveniles will be counted, which will indicate the effects of PPP mixtures on survival and reproduction, respectively. The size of adult springtails will also be measured using ImageJ software and indicate effects on adult growth.

Figure 2: Reproduction test with the springtail *Folsomia candida*.

2.3 Earthworms

Earthworms (Figure 3) are dependent on soil management, so under the presence of pollutants as PPP, earthworms are affected at different levels (individual, population and community levels, Pelosi et al. 2014), therefore is important to test the effect PPP on them.

Following the EFSA guidelines, acute (LC50) and chronic (NOEC reproduction) toxicity thresholds for earthworms (*Eisenia fetida* and *Eisenia andrei*) will be used for testing mortality and reproduction. For that PECs were used to calculate toxicity/exposure ratio (Pelosi et al. 2021) of mixtures of PPP. The experimental design will consist in different mixtures and doses of PPP, with 5 replicas per treatment. According to the OECD 222 (2015), 10 adult earthworms will be located for 28 days in one or 2 litter glass containers with 500 to 600 g substrate (soil mixed with PPP), under control conditions of

temperature, moisture and light. The endpoints will be mortality, reproduction and behaviour changes.

Figure 3: Detail of an earthworm body (*Megascolecidae*).

2.4 Beneficial insects

Tests will be conducted to determine effects of PPP mixtures on the parasitic wasp *Aphidius rhopalosiphii* (Figure 4) following the protocol of Mead-Briggs et al. (2000). The test will measure mortality of adult wasps and fecundity of female wasps exposed to the chosen mixtures. 10 adult wasps (at least 50% female) will be placed on a glass plate sprayed with a PPP mixture, with 4 replicates per treatment. Groups will be kept in a climate room at 20°C and 50-90% relative humidity. Mortality will then be recorded after 2, 24, and 48 hours, provided that control mortality does not exceed 12%. Following the exposure period (48 hours), at least 15 surviving female wasps per treatment will be removed and placed in pots containing aphid-infested wheat or barley for 24 hours. After 10 days the number of aphid mummies that develop will be counted. The reproductivity (i.e. mean number of mummies produced per wasp) can then be calculated and compared between treatments and controls. Mortality data will also be used to determine the LR50, which is the application rate that would result in 50% mortality.

Figure 4: The parasitoid wasp *Aphidius rhopalosiphii* that use aphids as their hosts

Experiments to determine the toxicity of the PPP mixtures will also be conducted for predatory mites (*Typhlodromus pyri*) following previously described methods (Blümel et al. 2000). This test measures the mortality of juveniles 7 days after exposure and the reproduction of females from 7-14 days post-exposure. Each treatment group will consist of 20 protonymphs with 5 replicates per treatment. The protonymphs will be placed on a glass plate sprayed with a PPP mixture and kept in a climate chamber at 25°C and 60-90% relative humidity. Mortality will be measured after 7 days, as long as the control mortality does not exceed 20%. Eggs and larvae will be removed from each plate on day 7. From day 7 until day 14, the number of eggs and juveniles per female will be recorded 3 times. This data will be used to determine reproductivity, measured as the mean cumulative number of eggs per female. The LR50 of the PPP mixture will also be calculated, which is the application rate that results in 50% mortality.

2.5 Bees

Oral toxicity test – honeybees and bumblebees

The acute oral toxicity of the selected PPP mixtures will be assessed following the OECD guidelines for both honeybees (*Apis mellifera*; OECD 1998) and bumblebees (*Bombus terrestris*; OECD 2017) (Figure 5). Young adult worker bees (i.e. nurse bees) will be collected in the summer from 3 colonies, representing independent replicates. These bees will be separated into treatment groups of 10 bees per cage. Bumblebees may be housed separately if there is mortality induced by worker conflicts. Treatments include control groups and at least four different doses of each PPP mixture administered through sucrose solution. Following exposure, mortality will be recorded after 4 hours, 24 hours, and 48 hours, provided that the control mortality does not exceed 10%. This test will be conducted in a dark climate chamber, at a temperature of 25°C and relative humidity of 70% for honeybees and 60% for bumblebees. The mortality data will then be used to plot dose-response curves at each observation time (24 and 48 hours) and the median lethal dose (LD50) will be calculated. The LD50 of the PPP mixture represents the dose at which honeybees will reach 50% mortality.

Figure 5: Honeybees (Apis mellifera, left) and bumblebees (Bombus terrestris)

Results from the oral toxicity test for honeybees and bumblebees will be analyzed to infer possible interactions between chemicals. The LD50s of each PPP mixture will be compared with the LD50s of the single components, which can be retrieved from literature and online databases such as ECOTOX (US EPA 2021). For example, a PPP mixture may have synergistic effects if it is more toxic than expected based on the component toxicity. Marking's additive index is one possible method to infer possible interactions in PPP mixtures and has previously been used to evaluate toxicity of mixtures of up to 8 components in honeybees (Wang et al. 2020).

Gut microbiota – honeybees and bumblebees

The impacts of the chosen PPP mixtures on the gut microbiota of honeybees and bumblebees will also be assessed. The relative and absolute abundance of different species (bacteria, fungi, etc.) in the microbiota

will be compared between bees exposed to varying doses of PPP mixtures and untreated bees (Figure 6). Adult worker bees will be collected between late spring and early fall from at least 3 different colonies, with each colony representing a replicate. These bees will be randomly grouped into cup cages previously described by other studies, with 30 bees per cup (Evans et al. 2009). Each cage will receive a different treatment, including a field-relevant dose, 3 additional doses and a control group for each PPP mixture, totalling 55 experimental units. Bees will be exposed to each PPP mixture orally through sterile sucrose solution. Following exposure, bees will be held for at least 10 days in a dark climate chamber at to emulate hive conditions.

Figure 6: Schematic showing distribution of bacterial communities in the honey bee worker gut. The ileum and rectum are two regions of the hindgut (Raymann and Moran 2018)

Afterwards, bees will be stored in the -80°C freezer and sterilized. The alimentary canal will then be removed with sterile forceps over ice and separated into the midgut, ileum, and rectum. The samples will be stored at -80°C until further analysis. DNA of the microbial community will then be extracted following protocol that includes a bead-beating step, as described by Engel et al. (2013). The extracted DNA will then be amplified with qPCR analysis using primers targeting the 16S rRNA gene. These samples will then be sent for sequencing and later analyzed to assign operational taxonomic units (OTUs) to each sample. Both alpha and beta diversities will be analyzed using QIIME. Gut microbial communities may also be compared using principal coordinates analysis (PCoA).

Honeybee and bumblebee colony exposure to PPP mixtures

Colony-level effects of the 11 chosen PPP mixtures will be monitored for honeybees and bumblebees. Testing the effects of exposure to 11 mixtures at 5 doses would require an excessive number of colonies. However, nucleus colonies (nucs) offer a feasible alternative, as they are smaller than full colonies yet fully functional. A feeder will be placed in each nuc and filled with sugar syrup spiked with different doses of each PPP mixture. The amount of brood and food resources will then be measured to monitor the impacts of the PPP mixtures on colony health, following previously described protocols (Meikle and Weiss 2017).

The effects of PPP mixtures on full colonies may also be assessed for a selection of mixtures. 2-3 PPP mixtures that pose a particularly high risk to honeybees and bumblebees will be chosen based on the results of the acute oral toxicity tests. These colonies will be chronically exposed to these PPP mixtures through sugar syrup and monitored over a year. Colony size, amount of brood, amount of food resources, and colony survival will be recorded and compared between treated hives and controls.

2.6 Plants

As primary producers, terrestrial plants are the base of food web, producing energy for other trophic levels. With the increasing use of PPPs, especially herbicides, it is important to know their effects on non-target plants. Therefore, toxicity tests with plants are not only necessary to fully address the impacts of PPPs, but also to assess the habitat function of contaminated soils.

Toxicity tests with terrestrial plants will be performed using one monocot (*Triticum aestivum*) and one dicot species (*Lactuca sativa*). Root growth test and seedling emergence and growth test will be performed following the ISO 11269-1 and ISO 11269-2 guidelines, respectively (Figure 7). Both tests will be conducted using at 4 concentrations of PPP mixtures and a control. Four replicates per treatment will be prepared. One day before starting the tests, soil will be spiked with the PPP mixtures and moisture adjusted to 50% WHC. If PPP mixture is added in solvent, a solvent control will be prepared, and samples will be allowed to evaporate overnight under a fume hood. Soil pH will be measured at the beginning of the tests.

In the root growth test, seeds will be pre-germinated in Petri dishes containing filter paper soaked in distilled water at 20 °C in dark for 48 to 60 h. Six germinated seeds will be sown into glass tubes (8 cm in diameter, 11 cm in height) containing 250 g of soil. Four replicates per treatment will be prepared. Plants will be grown in a climate room at 22±2 °C and a photoperiod of 16 h:8 h (light:dark). After 4 days, plants will be removed from jars, and roots and shoots separated. Roots will be gently washed, and root length will be measured. The dry weight of roots will be recorded after lyophilization.

In the seedling emergence and growth test, 10 seeds will be planted in pots containing 500 g of soil. Pots will be placed in a climate room at 22±2 °C and a photoperiod of 16 h:8 h (light:dark). The soil moisture content will be replenished regularly (three times a week). Plants will be checked daily for emergence, and the test will be run for 21 days after 50% of control plants have emerged. At the end of this period, percentage of emergence will be recorded, and shoots will be harvested at the soil surface. Shoot height and dry weight will be measured in fresh and lyophilized shoots, respectively.

Figure 7: Seedling emergence and growth test (right) and root growth test (left) with terrestrial plants.

3 Terrestrial tests – new SPRINT indicators

3.1 Soil microcosms

The soil microcosms planned for the SPRINT study were recently used several times for different pesticide related studies (Fojtová et al., 2019; Šudoma et al., 2019; Šudoma et al., 2020). Transparent glass flower pots of conical shape (12 cm height, 10 cm bottom width, 14 cm upper width) will be used as microcosms (Figure 8). One kg of spiked soil will be weighted in each pot. Then, 10-20 adult earthworms (species to be decided, probably *Apporectodea caliginosa* or *Lumbricus rubellus*) will be added to each pot together with 8 seeds of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*; pre-germinated 24 hours on a wet filter paper). The bottoms of the pots will be wrapped in aluminium foil and the ridge from parafilm was placed on the top. The soil moisture content will be adjusted every two days, and dried manure regularly added to feed the earthworms (2 g twice a month after the first month). All microcosms will be incubated in a conditions-controlled greenhouse.

The sampling will be done after 1d, 7d, 14d, 28d, 56d and optionally 112d. At the time-point, one set of the microcosms is sacrificed: 1) plants are removed, washed with water and dried with paper, root and leaves are separated and frozen; 2) earthworms are collected from the soil, washed, dried, weighted, placed into a Petri dish with wet filter paper to dehydrate, and the next day the worms washed, dried, weighted and frozen; 3) soil portion is frozen for PPP analysis; 4) soil portion is analysed for various microbial parameters.

Figure 8: The soil microcosms

3.2 Soil microbiome

Microorganisms play an important role in the nutrient cycle and the degradation of contaminants such as PPPs in the soil. A variety of different microorganisms are involved in those processes and their diversity can be used as indicators for the soil health. Furthermore, the different microbial groups are subject to changes due to environmental disturbances (e.g. PPP application) in their community structure and abundance. Next to this, the functional diversity and activity of the microbial community is of interest, since different processes need to take place to degrade different substances. For this, the activity of extracellular enzymes involved in C, N and P cycling are of interest for both the functional diversity as well as for the activity of the soil microbial community. Another approach to measure the potential functional diversity of the soil microbial community will be tested and performed if applicable. This approach is based on quantifying functional genes that code for enzymes involved in nutrient cycling (N, P) and PPP degradation. As such this can indicate the potential of the microbial community to degrade contaminants such as PPP. Pre-tests will be performed using local soil samples that will be spiked with mixtures of pesticides. Furthermore, soil from the microcosms (~220 samples) (Chapter 3.1) will be used for the analyses of microbial parameters.

To determine the soil microbial diversity the phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) analysis will be used. The PLFA analysis is performed following the modified ISO/TS 29843 and according to Frostegård et al. (1991). The method description is based on Kandeler et al. (2019). Briefly, 2 g thawed field moist soil are extracted with a solvent of chloroform, methanol and citrate buffer (pH 4) (1:2:0.8 v/v/v) (Bligh & Dyer 1959). The extract is separated using silica acid SPE cartridges (Bond Elut SI, 500 mg, 3 ml, Agilent Technologies Inc, Santa Clara, CA, USA), where only PLFAs are collected. Using an alkaline methanolysis (Kramer et al. 2012), PLFAs are transformed into fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) and measured on a gas chromatograph (GC) (AutoSystem XL, Perkin Elmer Inc., USA) equipped with an HP-5 capillary column and flame ionisation detector with helium as the carrier gas. PLFA FAMES are assigned to the microbial groups according to Ruess & Chamberlain (2010).

The determination of potential activities of extracellular enzymes involved in the C, N and P cycle will be performed following the modified ISO 20130 and according to Marx et al. (2001). The method description is based on Kandeler et al. (2019). The enzymes β -glucosidase (EC 3.2.1.21), β -xylosidase (EC 3.2.1.37), N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase (EC 3.2.1.52) and acid phosphatase (EC 3.1.3.2) are measured as follows: one g thawed field moist soil is suspended in 50 ml sterile water and disaggregated via sonication for 120 s at 50 J s⁻¹. A volume of 50 μ l constantly stirred soil solution is transferred in triplicate into microplate wells (PP microplate, black 96 well, Greiner Bio-one GmbH, Germany), mixed with 50 μ l MES-buffer (pH 6.1) and 100 μ l of fluorescent 4-methylumbelliferone (4-MUF) linked substrates (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, USA). Before measurement, all microplates are pre-incubated for 30 min at 30 °C. The fluorescence of the samples is measured at 360/460 nm (excitation/measurement) after 0, 30, 60, 120 and 180 min using a fluorescence microplate reader (FLx800, BioTek Instruments Inc., USA). The incubation temperature between measurements is 30 °C, and a standard plate with concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 2.5, 4, and 6 μ M MUF is carried through every measurement series.

DNA will be isolated by WUR on the principle of the Qiagen PowerSoil DNA isolation kit. Briefly, 1 g of soil is added to 3 ml bead solution and 0.24 mL of an SDS-based lysis buffer. Carbide beads (1.5 g) are added to increase extraction efficiency. Tubes are shaken for 15 min at a Digital Vortex genie 2 (SI-A256) with a SI-H512 horizontal 15 ml tube holder at maximum speed (2,850 rpm). After centrifuging, the supernatant is abstracted from humic acids using first 1 mL of ammonium acetate, followed by 0.8 mL of an ammonium aluminum sulfate dodecahydrate solution. Silica spin filter (RP20 CommaPrep RNA extraction column, Biocomma, China) are used to bind the nucleic acids and subsequently purify the DNA. DNA quantity are measured with nanodrop and a selection of samples with Qubit in order to ensure yield is sufficient. Until further processing, nucleic acid eluates are stored in -20 °C.

The abundance of genes encoding for enzymes involved in pesticide degradation, nitrogen cycle and phosphate cycle (see Appendix 1) will be determined by quantitative PCR (qPCR). The method description is based on Teste et al. (2021). Briefly, for each qPCR reaction a master mix containing 7.5 μl SYBR Green (Applied Biosystems), an adjusted amount of the individual forward and reverse primer, 0.375 μl T4gp32 and an adjusted amount of PCR-grade water is added to 1 to 2 μl of DNA (5 ng μl^{-1}). These amounts were tested and verified in preliminary experiments. The abundance of the genes are determined using the 7500 Fast Real-Time PCR System (Applied Biosystems, USA). A complete list of all genes, their function, primers, reaction conditions and references is given in Appendix 1.

Indicate time when you analyse all this and which is the initial soil microbiome

3.3 Native earthworms

Earthworms as soil ecosystem engineers contribute with their activity on several ecosystem services as soil organic matter decomposition, infiltration, and the availability of nutrients to the plants, therefore, when pollutants as pesticides are present in the soil, earthworms are affected, and the mentioned ecosystem services are jeopardized. Therefore, earthworms are good indicators of soil quality and assessing the risk of PPP on them is relevant.

Following the same procedure presented above (OECD, 2022), three previous selected earthworms species abundant in the CSSs belonging to the 3 ecological categories (epigeic (*A. chlorotica* or/and *L. rubellus*), endogeic (*A. caliginosa*) and anecic (*L. terrestris*)) will be assessed. Five to seven treatments (combination of PPP mixtures with different doses, and single or mix of earthworm species) and 5 replicas per treatment will be implemented in control conditions of light, moisture and temperature. The endpoints are mortality and reproduction (cocoons production per worm).

3.4 Native insects

The effects of the PPP mixtures will also be tested on insects native to the CSS. Species will be chosen based on the ground-dwelling insects found in each CSS, such as the carabid beetle *Poecilus cupreus*. Species determinations of the ground-dwelling insects will be completed in early 2022, after which representative species will be chosen. Each of these species will be exposed to varying doses of PPP mixtures to establish a dose-response relationship. This will be used to determine the median lethal dose (LD50). Additionally, microcosm experiments will be performed to determine the effects of mixtures on communities of ground-dwelling insects.

4 Aquatic tests – EFSA standards

4.1 Microalgae

Unicellular microalgae have been used as an effective biomarker of environmental pollution. They occupy an initial and key role in the food web as producers. Moreover, they quickly respond to chemical contamination of the environment.

Tests with the green microalgae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* will be performed following the standard OECD protocol 201 with adaptations for microplate use (OECD 2011a). Algal cultures established in the laboratory under axenic conditions will be used for the tests. Microalgae exposure will be conducted in 24-well sterile plates considering 4 replicates per PPP mixture concentration plus a control (MBL culture medium). Each well will be inoculated with an initial cell concentration of 10^4 cells mL⁻¹. The tests will be incubated at the same conditions of temperature ($24 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) and illumination (6000 lux) used for culturing. After 72 h to 96h of exposure, the algae growth inhibition rate will be calculated by measuring optical density at 440 nm, in both control and tested concentrations.

Figure 10: a) Cultures of green microalgae in 100 ml Erlenmeyers; b) 24 well microplates used to expose the microalgae to contaminants

4.2 Aquatic plants

Plant-based ecotoxicological studies have the potential to identify possible toxicological risks in the environment, since contamination phenomena observed in the plants may affect all the other organisms and the health of the entire ecosystem, including humans.

The growth inhibition test using the aquatic plant *Lemna minor* will be performed according to the OECD guideline 221 (OECD 2006a). Cultures maintained in axenic conditions in an acclimated chamber under controlling illumination (8000 lux) and temperature ($24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) will be used to conduct the tests. The exposures will be carried out in sterilized 150 mL Erlenmeyer's, filled with 100 mL of Steinberg culture medium. A total of 3 colonies with three visible fronds will initially exposed per replicate (four replicates per PPP mixture concentration plus the control). The number of fronds and corresponding fresh and dry weight will be measured per replicate, after 7 days of exposure, allowing the calculation of the growth rate.

Figure 11: a) Cultures of *L. minor* in 250 ml erlenmeyers; b) 150 ml erlenmeyers used to expose the aquatic plants to contaminants

4.3 Aquatic insects

Among the aquatic macroinvertebrates, chironomids are one of the most widespread and often abundant group of insects in freshwater environments. They provide an important link between different trophic levels and play a key role in recycling organic matter and thus in the aquatic ecosystem functioning. Additionally, as they inhabit in the sediment-water interface, assays with chironomids also allow to simulate accumulated levels of chemicals persisting in the sediment.

Lethal and sub-lethal toxicity assays using *Chironomus riparius* will be conducted using the OECD guidelines 235 and 218, respectively. Chironomid larvae will be obtained from laboratory cultures maintained at 20 ± 2 °C, with a 16 hL: 8 hD photoperiod. The culture unit supports the whole life cycle of the chironomids. Freshly laid egg masses are kept in Petri dishes with ASTM until hatching. A suspension of grinded fish food (TetraMin®; 1 mg larvae-1 day-1) is added as the food source. For the lethal tests larvae will be exposed to spiked water in 100-mL plastic flasks and no food will be offered. At least 20 animals divided into four groups of five animals each, will be used for each test concentration and controls (consisting of ASTM culture medium). Immobility will be used as surrogate parameter for lethality, and it will be measured at 24 and 48h. Concerning the sub-lethal assays, first instar chironomid larvae will be exposed to PPP mixtures concentrations plus a control in 600 ml beakers filled with culture medium and sediment. The PPP mixtures will be spiked into the sediment and first instar larvae are subsequently introduced into test beakers in which the sediment and water concentrations have been stabilized. Chironomid emergence and development rate will be measured at the end of the test (28 days). Larval survival and weight will also be measured after 10 days

Figure 12: a) Boxes used for chironomid cultures, b) beakers used to run the assays

4.4 Fish

As fish respond with a greater sensitivity to changes in the aquatic environment, they are considered an effective indicator to assess contamination in aquatic ecosystems as well as to infer the potential risks for human health due to their consumption. A great number of characteristics make them excellent models in aquatic ecotoxicology, especially for the contaminants which are likely to exert their impact on aquatic system, as PPPs.

The ecotoxicological assessment will comprise tests with fish embryos, namely the fish embryo toxicity test (FET) with the zebrafish *Danio rerio*, following the OECD guideline 236. This test is a replacement for the originally proposed standard tests with juvenile or adult fish, guided by the 3R's (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement) policy.

Adult fish that will supply the eggs for the toxicity tests are housed in a certificate Zebrafish facility. Tests will be carried out with newly fertilized eggs (3-4 h post-fertilization). Fish eggs will be exposed to the experimental concentrations (control + 3 PPP mixture concentrations + 1 real field concentration) in 24-well plates, with 20 replicates per treatment. Tests will be conducted at 26 ± 1 °C and under a 16 hL:8 hD photoperiod regime. Daily, through the 96 h of the test duration, embryos will be observed and checked for different endpoints: survival, occurrence of deformities, heartbeat (measured following 48 h of exposure in all replicates by counting total beats in 15 s) and hatching success.

Figure 12: Zebrafish facility

5 Aquatic tests – new SPRINT indicators

5.1 Multi-species microcosm assays

For the aquatic ecosystem, a microcosm combining three distinct trophic levels will be implemented using a simplified trophic chain model, including microbial decomposers, plant litter and a macroinvertebrate decomposer (e.g. shredders). The multi-species microcosms will also be used to evaluate the potential for trophic transfer of PPPs.

Figure 13: Set-up used for the microcosms experiments with freshwater species

6 Conclusion

As the available information on the ecotoxicity of PPP compounds is mostly based on the effects of single compounds, the outcomes of SPRINT WP4 will foster the existing knowledge providing novel ecotoxicological information on the effects of PPP mixtures on terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Beside the assays with standard species, native species will be also exposed to the selected PPP mixtures, generating important ecotoxicological to better infer on the impacts of PPP mixtures on local communities. Furthermore, by using a stepwise approach, from single-species tests with organisms to multi-species microcosm SPRINT WP4 will also allow to assess the potential for bioconcentration and biomagnification through the trophic chain and indirect exposures and effects.

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